

**D5.2 Report on the Procedure
to identify research and
integrative needs of
international stakeholders**

**WP5 Science to policy
translation to stakeholders**

Responsible Partner: SSI

Contributing partners: BfR, PMT members

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Leader	Kåre Mølbak, SSI
Other contributors	Pikka Jokelainen, SSI, Annemarie Käsbohrer, BfR, the One Health EJP Project Management Team members
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Matrix of identified research and integrative needs of international stakeholders. First version.

1. Summary

This report describes the Procedure to identify research and integrative needs of international stakeholders of the One Health EJP, and reports on the status of this process in February 2018.

2. Introduction

The overall objective of the European Joint Programme (EJP) One Health EJP (Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards) is to develop a European network of research institutes, mainly with reference laboratory functions. The EJP will integrate medical, veterinary, and food scientists in the field of food and feed safety in order to improve research on the prevention and control of mainly foodborne zoonoses, whilst taking into account the public health concerns of consumers and other stakeholders throughout the food chain. Following a One Health approach the EJP aims to create a sustainable European One Health framework by integration and alignment of medical, veterinary, and food institutes **through joint programming of research agendas matching the needs of European and national policy makers and stakeholders.**

One of the specific objectives of One Health EJP is to exchange and communicate with all national and international stakeholders, and in particular the European Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (ECDC) and the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA). Stakeholder liaison actions include developing and maintaining contact with ECDC and EFSA to ensure that the overall objectives of the One Health EJP consortium are in accordance with the overarching policies of the respective agencies in relation to foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance, and emerging threats.

The One Health EJP is structured into seven work packages (WP) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Structure of One Health EJP. Work package 5 (WP5) focuses on science-to-policy translation to stakeholders, which are shown in the bottom of the figure.

Work package 5 (WP5) of One Health EJP is entitled ‘Science to policy translation to stakeholders’ and it is active during the whole length of One Health EJP (2018–2022, 60 months). The Lead Beneficiary is Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) and the Deputy Lead Beneficiary is Statens Serum Institut (SSI). The purpose of WP5 is to establish a dialogue with EFSA and ECDC as well as EU policy makers as major stakeholders of the One Health EJP and also with other relevant international policy makers (WHO, OIE, FAO) and national stakeholders (national ministries and the mirror groups, if these are established). The needs identified by the risk-assessors will be taken into account in the procedure for updating strategic priorities defined in WP2. WP5 will also function as a channel for the One Health EJP to disseminate new scientific data to these stakeholders. Overall, WP5 aims to enhance the visibility and the usefulness of this EJP among policy makers and EU agencies.

The objectives of WP5 are:

- To develop procedures for an efficient information flow and interaction between science and European stakeholders (EU policy makers and EU agencies)
- To advocate for the One Health EJP and the One Health approach among EU policy makers (EC) and EU agencies (ECDC and EFSA)
- To communicate to the One Health EJP governing structure the research and integrative needs identified in policy processes of the European Commission and need for knowledge identified by the EU agencies (ECDC and EFSA)
- Vice-versa, to highlight how and when data resulting from activities within the One Health EJP could be used to improve policy initiatives, including risk management practices that addresses the protection of consumers health
- To support alignment of the scientific capacity within the consortium with other similar activities in EC member states in collaboration with WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP6.
- Together with WP1, communicate the scientific evidence based data to the EU stakeholders, the international stakeholders (WHO, OIE, FAO) and within the Member States

To achieve these objectives, collaboration with stakeholders will be established and procedures implemented to identify stakeholder's needs in the fields of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats. A procedure to identify research and integrative needs of international stakeholders is required to ensure that the research and integrative needs of the stakeholders are efficiently received by One Health EJP. Identification of the research and integrative needs of the stakeholders includes regular scanning of available documents and transparent dialogue with the stakeholders, with focus on the Key EU stakeholders ECDC and EFSA (D5.1). The procedure includes close collaboration with the PMT and the Stakeholders Committee.

This report describes the Procedure to identify research and integrative needs of international stakeholders, and reports on the status of this process in February 2018.

3. Setting and focus of Procedure to identify research and integrative needs of international stakeholders

3.1. International stakeholders

The international stakeholders of One Health EJP include EU stakeholders, global stakeholders, and regional stakeholders (D5.1). The WP5 actions related to identifying research and integrative needs of international stakeholders are highly **focused on the Key EU stakeholders ECDC and EFSA** (D5.1). Their input is the main focus in particular in the very beginning of the One Health EJP, where their input can have the greatest impact. The first identified research and integrative needs will be provided for consideration for inclusion in the Strategic Research Agenda (WP2), which will be the basis for the second call for Joint Research projects (WP3) and Joint Integrative projects (WP4).

3.2. Research and integrative needs

The main focus is on research and integrative needs in **areas where a One Health approach is essential**. The EU stakeholders should serve as a network to raise knowledge gaps as regards e.g. emerging threats or other hazards that falls **within the scope of the One Health EJP**, and key functionality where preparedness, detection, and response can be improved by an intersectoral approach. The Key EU stakeholders ECDC and EFSA are in the position to have identified which knowledge gaps, when filled, could have the highest value for informing decision-making in EU, and also for which collaborative processes a higher degree of alignment and integration will strengthen EU resilience the most. The research needs need to be described in sufficient detail including all relevant aspects (such as setting, timing, populations, interventions, outcomes). Moreover, the reasoning for the gap may be relevant for finding the optimal approach to fill it. Integrative needs should be described in terms of current state of the art, the desired capacity, and drivers and constraints to development.

4. Procedure to identify research and integrative needs of international stakeholders

The Procedure to identify research and integrative needs of international stakeholders is based on the scanning of available documents (e.g. strategic research and innovation agendas, scientific opinions, and risk assessments of the stakeholders) and on direct and transparent dialogue with the stakeholders.

The main aim is to identify the research needs that are knowledge gaps that, when filled, could have the highest value for informing decision-making in EU. This may be specified by different aspects of the research needs, such as the setting, timing, populations, interventions, and outcomes that are of importance to the stakeholders. Similarly, the process aims to identify key preparedness, detection and response capacity where there is a need or an opportunity for improved by applying an intersectoral approach, and where a higher degree of alignment and integration is a priority for improving overall EU resilience. A further aim is to avoid topics that are already being addressed in other activities. This can be achieved by transparent dialogue with the stakeholders, other research consortia (via WP2), and within the One Health EJP.

A systematic scanning and analysis procedure to screen the internet and EU stakeholders' webpages for relevant documents (e.g. risk assessments, scientific opinions) for identified research and integrative needs will be implemented and regularly run. The documents are identified from the websites of the stakeholders and using internet search engines. Further documents are identified using snowball approach from the identified documents, by consulting the stakeholders contact list, and by asking for input from the One Health EJP consortium. The document list is made available for the One Health EJP consortium and on the platform for dialogue with the stakeholders. Explicitly expressed research and integrative needs and knowledge gaps, as well as needs for improved preparedness are extracted and added to the matrix of identified research needs of international stakeholders. The main method is traditional systematic screening, but novel, innovative text analysis tools (e.g. text mining tools, word clouds) may be experimented for this use. Four times a year, the list of documents is updated and the new documents are scanned. The systematic scanning focuses largely on documents of the two Key EU stakeholders, but the approach may be applied to other Key stakeholders.

The stakeholders are actively involved as informants and engaged at the most relevant times during the One Health EJP; the dialogue is maintained active throughout the duration of One Health EJP. On the website of One Health EJP, a technical platform for interaction with the stakeholders to identify research and integrative needs and for other requests for scientific support will be established. In collaboration with WP1, specific tools for communication with stakeholders will be implemented, e.g. by providing restricted areas on the website or within a virtual research environment. The platform is not available from the very beginning of One Health EJP. The dialogue was initiated by invitations to the Stakeholders Committee, continued at the One Health EJP Kick-Off Meeting (KOM) in January 2018 by presentations, and is being continued mainly by emails until the platform is available (Communication procedure, D5.1).

A matrix of identified research and integrative needs of international stakeholders is created. Information included in the matrix are:

1. date of adding the gap/need into the matrix
2. source (from where the gap/need is extracted, who presented it)
3. original description of the gap/need (as in the source)
4. whether a One Health approach is considered essential for the research or integrative need (discussed with stakeholders 1 – 4 times a year)
5. whether the research or integrative need is within the scope of One Health EJP (evaluated by PMT, which WP5 consults, 1 – 4 times a year)
6. whether the research or integrative need is already being addressed in other activities (collaboration and consultation of WP2, 1 – 4 times a year)
7. keywords (added by WP5, all)
8. WP2 matrix keywords (added by WP5, WP2, PMT)
9. if considered within the scope of One Health EJP (point 5.) and not being addressed in other activities (point 6.): description of the research or integrative need, including all relevant details (formulated by WP5, discussed actively with the relevant stakeholders).

The matrix may be further developed or adapted to another format during the One Health EJP. Important functions include sorting and searching using keywords.

5. Actions taken on the identified research or integrative needs of international stakeholders

The identified research and integrative needs and gaps in knowledge and preparedness are discussed with the stakeholders. At first, this is done by emails and include the first Stakeholders contact list focusing on the Key EU stakeholders ECDC and EFSA. As soon as the technical platform is available, the discussion will be moved there.

The stakeholders will be explicitly asked to evaluate whether a One Health approach is essential for the identified research and integrative needs and gaps in knowledge and preparedness (point 4.). This will be done in a scale from 0 – 5 (0 = not essential at all, 5 = highly essential) and marked in the matrix. This step encourages considering One Health thinking and approach, and the evaluation informs the actions of WP2 and WP7.

The list of identified research and integrative needs and gaps in knowledge and preparedness is consolidated by two exclusion steps and formulation of the research or integrative needs in sufficient and relevant detail. First, WP5 will ask PMT to evaluate whether the identified research and integrative needs and gaps in knowledge and preparedness are within the scope of One Health EJP (point 5.). Despite the stakeholders are informed of the scope and focus of the One Health EJP, it is expected that some of the needs identified do not fall within the scope of One Health EJP. Such needs are moved to a separate sheet in the matrix file. Then, WP5 will ask WP2 to evaluate whether the identified research and integrative needs and gaps in knowledge and preparedness are already being addressed e.g. in the Joint Research projects or Joint Integrative projects, or in other activities known to the One Health EJP consortium (point 6.). If a need or a gap is already being addressed, there is likely no longer a need. Needs identified as topics that are already being addressed in other activities are moved to a separate sheet in the matrix file.

WP5 will formulate the description of the research and integrative needs remaining listed after the two exclusion steps (point 9.). The descriptions of research needs should include all relevant details, such as setting, timing, populations, interventions, outcomes, and reason for the gap. For integrative needs, state of the art, the desired capacity, as well as drivers and constraints to development should be described. This process includes dialogue with the stakeholders. The dialogue takes place using

different forms of communication, including emails, the platform, and face-to-face discussions during the One Health EJP.

It should be emphasized that further classifying and prioritising processes of topics for the second call for Joint Research projects (WP2WP3) and Joint Integrative Activities projects (WP4) are separate from this procedure (will take place within WP2) i.e. these topics are not further prioritised by the actions of WP5. PMT will make the prioritising decisions on later upcoming research needs that the One Health EJP could respond quickly to (small projects, of clearly more limited extent than the projects from first and second call) or that could be addressed in case studies run within integrative activities (WP4).

A consolidated list of the identified research and integrative needs will be used to give input to work in the consortium as well as further dialogue with the stakeholders. The list will be made available for the consortium as well as on the platform where dialogue with the stakeholders (D5.1) takes place, on the website of One Health EJP.

The activities of WP5 ensure that the identified research and integrative needs will be efficiently absorbed by the One Health EJP. Approaches to fill identified knowledge or preparedness gaps will be developed and accomplished, where feasible. The first identified research and integrative needs will be provided for consideration for inclusion in the Strategic Research Agenda (WP2), which will be the basis for the second call for Joint Research projects (WP3) and Joint Integrative projects (WP4). This call will be launched immediately after the SSB meeting in September 2018. The provisional report on these research and integrative needs is due in April 2018 (M4).

Later, the focus changes to upcoming research needs that the One Health EJP could respond quickly to, and topics that could be addressed in case studies run within integrative activities (WP4). A procedure to provide scientific support to stakeholders, e.g. by executing specific work (small projects, of clearly more limited extent than the projects from first and second call) will be developed. Moreover, a mechanism will be developed to provide, to the best extent feasible, *ad hoc* support to stakeholders in case of emerging threats, where scientific support needs may arise quickly.

Actions within WP5 ensure the best use of expertise in the consortium, communication (dialogue with the stakeholders), and dissemination (tailored dissemination to the stakeholders). All identified research and integrative needs will inform development of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (WP7).

6. Status in February 2018

The first version of the matrix of identified research and integrative needs of international stakeholders is Annex 1 of this report.

The first document scanning is being performed and the preliminary list of documents is compiled and the first round extraction of research and integrative needs and gaps in knowledge and preparedness from the documents is done by the end of February 2018.

The Stakeholders Committee members of the two Key EU stakeholders ECDC and EFSA were invited to present their expectations to the One Health EJP at the KOM. Research and integrative needs are extracted from these presentations and included in the matrix of identified research and integrative needs of international stakeholders. These research and integrative needs were presented directly to the One Health EJP.

Further dialogue will be initiated by email in March 2018 and will include the first Stakeholders contact list, which will be compiled by the end of February 2018 (D5.1), and PMT and WP2 for the exclusion steps.

The first consolidated list of identified research and integrative needs will be provided for consideration for inclusion in the Strategic Research Agenda (WP2), which will be the basis for the second call for Joint Research projects (WP3) and Joint Integrative projects (WP4). The provisional report on the first identified research and integrative needs is deliverable D5.3 which is due in April 2018 (M4).

7. List of abbreviations

BfR	Federal Institute for Risk Assessment
EC	European Commission
ECDC	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
EDA	European Defence Agency
EEA	European Environment Agency
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EJP	European Joint Programme
EMA	European Medicines Agency
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
KOM	Kick-off Meeting
M2	Month 2, second month of One Health EJP: February 2018
OIE	World Organisation for Animal Health
PMT	The Project Management Team
SSI	Statens Serum Institut
WP	Work Package
WHO	World Health Organization

